

Reconstructing a medieval recipe for red lead (Pb_3O_4): an archaeometric approach

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ABSTRACT

In this study, we experimentally reconstructed a medieval synthesis of red lead based on recipes from Theophilus's 12th-century treatise. Controlled transformation rate thermal analysis (CRTA) combined with high temperature diffraction provided insights into the phase transitions occurring during this preparation. Our results indicate that the pigment referred to as "minium" in historical sources does not always correspond to pure Pb_3O_4 , but may involve mixtures of PbCO_3 , $\text{PbCO}_3 \cdot 2\text{PbO}$, $\alpha\text{-PbO}$, and $\beta\text{-PbO}$, depending on the thermal and atmospheric conditions. This variability reflects both the metastability of Pb_3O_4 and the technological diversity of historical lead-based pigments.

By bridging experimental archaeology, historical reconstruction, and advanced materials characterization, this work contributes to a better understanding of medieval pigment production and its underlying chemical mechanisms. It highlights how archaeometry approaches can illuminate the interplay between craft knowledge and material science in the Middle Ages.

KEYWORDS

Minium; Medieval pigments; Historical recipes; CRTA; TGA; HT-XRD

INTRODUCTION

Until the twelfth century, manuscript production was largely confined to monastic scriptoria. From the thirteenth century onward, the growth of universities increased demand for books and fostered the development of lay workshops. As books became objects of prestige, richly decorated with illuminations, late medieval manuscripts emerged as valuable artistic and historical sources, shedding light on the materials, techniques, and workshop practices of illuminators.

In order to provide new insights into the notion of the illuminators' workshop, we chose to complete the *in situ* analyses of manuscripts¹ with a study and experimental reconstruction of medieval pigment recipes. Our aim here is to explore what illuminators actually did in their workshops when preparing their own pigments, how they did it, and why they carried out these processes in a particular way. From a chemical standpoint, the approach aims to identify the most plausible reaction mechanisms underlying the medieval production of each pigment and to evaluate the influence of empirically selected parameters on both the reaction pathway and the nature of the final product. Modern characterization techniques are therefore essential, as the purpose is not merely to reproduce historical recipes but to achieve a mechanistic understanding of the processes involved. Note that the reproduction or reworking of historical processes has only recently gained recognition in the history of chemistry^{2,3}. Today, it is increasingly used and acknowledged as a valuable complement to historical inquiry. In the field of heritage science, one notable precedent is the work of Gonzalez *et al.* (2019), who proposed the first reasoned, experiment-based reconstruction of a corrosion process described in historical sources — the 17th-century Dutch process⁴. To our knowledge, the present study is the first to apply an experimental approach specifically to the practices of medieval illuminators.

The primary source underpinning this study is the collection compiled by Jean Lebègue, entitled *Liber colorum*. Preserved at the Bibliothèque nationale de France, this manuscript consists of a compilation of technical recipes assembled in the early fifteenth century for the preparation of colours. It includes painting recipes dating from around 1400, such as those attributed to the Parisian illuminator Antoine de Compiègne, as well as earlier texts, notably the treatise of Theophilus, a twelfth-century monk who brought together in his *Schedula diversarum artium* a remarkable corpus of pigment recipes.

We propose to illustrate our approach by presenting the experimental reconstruction of the preparation of minium (Pb_3O_4). We selected this pigment because it occupies a singular position in the history of manuscripts: it is widely considered to be the compound that gave rise to the term “miniature” and must therefore have held a particular place on the illuminator's palette. Yet, we have found no trace whatsoever of this pigment in the Parisian manuscripts we have studied thus far. Faced with this contradiction, we chose to reproduce it in the laboratory, relying on the recipe described by

Theophilus in the section devoted to the preparation of ceruse (lead white)⁵: “*Grind ceruse [...] place it into two or three new vessels, set them on hot coals; take a thin curved iron [...] with which you can stir the ceruse from time to time. Continue until the minium becomes completely red.*” The recipe for minium is therefore based on the thermal decomposition of lead carbonate (lead white).

Despite more than sixty years of studies on the thermal decomposition of lead carbonate, the precise conditions required for minium (Pb_3O_4) formation remain poorly understood. Indeed, most previous investigations have focused on the pathways leading to PbO ⁶, leaving open questions concerning Pb_3O_4 formation; is this formation associated with a complete reaction? In other words, is it possible to obtain pure minium? If so, at what temperature does this transition occur? And if so, within what temperature range is minium stable? In order to address these questions and to better understand the reaction mechanisms involved in the recipe proposed by Theophilus for the preparation of minium, we investigated the decomposition of ceruse by Controlled Transformation Rate Thermal Analysis (CRTA) combined with high temperature X-ray diffraction (HT-XRD). CRTA enables quasi-equilibrium conditions, allowing the disentanglement of overlapping reactions and the proposal of a general mechanism for Pb_3O_4 formation^{7,8}. HT-XRD further confirms the sequence of structural transformations and provides direct evidence for the phases involved. To our knowledge, this combination of advanced thermal and structural methods is applied here for the first time in the field of heritage science. Our results offer new insights into both the chemistry of Pb_3O_4 synthesis and the material practices of medieval colour preparation.

EXPERIMENTAL

Materials. Ceruse (lead white) designates a pigment based on lead carbonate, present either as cerussite (PbCO_3), hydrocerussite ($2\text{PbCO}_3 \cdot \text{Pb}(\text{OH})_2$), or, more frequently, as a combination of both phases. As a reference system for our study, we selected the simpler phase, PbCO_3 , obtained from Kremer Pigments (ref. 46000).

Thermal analysis. Thermogravimetric analyses (TGA) were performed on ~72mg samples using a Q500 analyzer (TA Instruments). Conventional TGA experiments were conducted under flowing air ($40\text{mL} \cdot \text{min}^{-1}$), heating to 650°C at $4^\circ\text{C} \cdot \text{min}^{-1}$. Controlled Transformation Rate Thermal Analysis (CRTA) measurements were performed on the same instrument in constant reaction rate mode, under flowing air or argon ($40\text{mL} \cdot \text{min}^{-1}$).

X-ray diffraction. Powder XRD patterns were collected on a Siemens D5005 diffractometer with $\text{Cu-K}\alpha$ radiation ($20\text{--}40^\circ$ 2θ range, step size 0.04° , step time 2s). High temperature XRD was carried out in Bragg–Brentano geometry with a PANalytical X’Pert MPD diffractometer equipped with an

X'Ceerator detector. Measurements ($20\text{--}40^\circ 2\theta$ range, step size 0.04° , step time 50s) were performed in air using an Anton Paar HTK 1200 chamber, heating from room temperature to 650°C at $\sim 1.5^\circ\text{C}\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$.

Photography. Samples were documented with Nikon D800E (36MP) and Nikon D850E (45MP) cameras equipped with 60mm objectives. Images were acquired in the visible range with a Schott BG39 filter, illuminated by two Elinchrome Ranger lamps (1100 W). An X-Rite ColorChecker was used for calibration.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

1. Thermal analysis of the decomposition of lead carbonate

Figure 1 presents CRTA curves recorded for neutral lead carbonate (PbCO_3) under flowing air and argon. The experiments were conducted at a controlled reaction rate of $18.0\pm 0.1\text{mg}\cdot\text{h}^{-1}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$, with a total acquisition time of $\sim 10\text{h}$. The advantage of CRTA over conventional thermogravimetry is evident when comparing the thermal analysis curves obtained in air (Fig.2): the dashed line corresponds to conventional TGA, whereas the solid red line represents CRTA. In the latter, four distinct decomposition steps are clearly resolved, enabling mechanistic interpretation.

According to the CRTA data, the decomposition of PbCO_3 occurs between 20°C and 650°C , with a mass loss of $16.5\pm 0.1\%$ under both air and argon. This value matches the theoretical loss expected from the following reaction, confirmed by the XRD phase analysis (Fig. 3):

Figure 1

- (a) Thermal decomposition of lead carbonate monitored by Controlled Transformation Rate Thermal Analysis (CRTA) in flowing air (solid curve) and argon (dashed curve).
- (b) Experimental conditions correspond to a reaction rate of $18.0 \pm 0.1 \text{ mg} \cdot \text{h}^{-1} \cdot \text{g}^{-1}$.
- (c) Temperature profile recorded under constant decomposition rate conditions; analyses required approximately 10 hours.

Figure 2

Thermal decomposition of lead carbonate monitored by conventional thermogravimetry (dashed curve, heating rate = $4^{\circ}\text{C}\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$) and by CRTA (solid curve). Four well-resolved steps are identified (1–4).

Figure 3

X-ray diffraction patterns of the Kremer sample recorded at room temperature: (a) before CRTA and (b) after CRTA. The initial phase corresponds to pure cerussite, PbCO_3 (PDF 01-76-2056), while the final phase is pure massicot, $\beta\text{-PbO}$ (PDF 00-038-1477). Identical results were obtained under flowing argon.

All diffraction patterns recorded up to $240\pm 10^\circ\text{C}$ display only the PbCO_3 phase, characterized by intense reflections between 24° and 26° (Fig. 4). Notably, from $180\pm 10^\circ\text{C}$ onwards, these reflections gradually shift to lower angles, most likely due to lattice expansion upon heating. Above $240\pm 10^\circ\text{C}$, an additional reflection emerges at $\sim 29^\circ$, indicative of the formation of the $\text{PbCO}_3\cdot 2\text{PbO}$ phase, in agreement with the following reaction:

Figure 4

HT-X-ray diffraction of lead carbonate during heating ($1.5^\circ\text{C}\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$) from room temperature to 650°C , illustrating the four steps observed in the CRTA curve.

The temperature of $240\pm 10^\circ\text{C}$ identified for this reaction in the X-ray diffraction chamber is consistent with the features of the thermal analysis curve. On the CRTA trace, an inflection point is observed at $250\pm 2^\circ\text{C}$. This profile, commonly described as saddle-shaped—characterized by a transient decrease in temperature following the onset of decomposition—is indicative of a nucleation-and-growth mechanism⁹. As the reaction interface propagates, a lower temperature is sufficient to

maintain the reaction rate at the imposed level. The reaction is also found to be zero-order, as the decomposition temperature is independent of the extent of conversion. A similar phenomenon has been reported for the thermal decomposition of gibbsite, where the isothermal stage arises from the advance of a reactive interface parallel to the largest crystal face. By analogy, the zero-order behaviour observed here can be assigned a clear physical significance.

Importantly, diffraction patterns reveal that the reaction does not proceed to completion (Fig. 4). Even at 260°C, a substantial fraction of lead carbonate remains in the sample. This thermodynamic limitation is corroborated by CRTA data: while the reaction equation predicts a theoretical mass loss of 11%, the experimental value is only 9.0±0.1% under both air and argon atmospheres.

In contrast to step one, which is characterized by a constant decomposition temperature of 220°C, step two exhibits a decomposition temperature that gradually increases from 220°C to 330°C in air, as shown by the CRTA curve. This behaviour suggests that the underlying mechanism is more complex than that proposed for step one. The X-ray diffraction pattern recorded at 290±10°C reveals residual lead carbonate (PbCO₃) together with the PbCO₃·2PbO phase, whereas the pattern collected at 300 ± 10°C shows only PbCO₃·2PbO and α-PbO. The slope change observed in the CRTA curve around 220°C can therefore be attributed to the two simultaneous reactions described below.

As shown by the diffraction pattern recorded at 330±10°C in the X-ray diffraction chamber, step two concludes with the single transformation of PbCO₃·2PbO into α-PbO. Notably, this step is complete in the thermal analysis performed under argon, emphasizing the influence of the surrounding atmosphere on the thermodynamic parameters—a key factor in understanding and reproducing the medieval preparation of red lead. Moreover, the reaction order under argon remains zero, as previously demonstrated for step one. We therefore conclude that the second stage of decomposition is governed by two parallel reactions (reactions (1) and (2)), with reaction (2) remaining incomplete.

At 360±10°C, XRD patterns show PbCO₃·2PbO, α-PbO, and Pb₃O₄, confirming that two reactions take place concurrently.

Subsequently, the intensities of the characteristic peaks of $\text{PbCO}_3 \cdot 2\text{PbO}$ and $\alpha\text{-PbO}$ decrease rapidly, and the Pb_3O_4 phase becomes dominant after one hour at $380^\circ\text{C} \pm 10^\circ\text{C}$. These observations are corroborated by the CRTA curve: reaction (3) is associated with a theoretical mass loss, whereas reaction (4) corresponds to a theoretical mass gain. The plateau observed on the CRTA curve therefore indicates that these two reactions occur simultaneously during the third stage. Furthermore, the diffraction patterns demonstrate that Pb_3O_4 remains stable over a wide temperature range, suggesting that the plateau may also reflect the intrinsic thermal stability of Pb_3O_4 within this interval.

A slope break is observed on the CRTA curve at $410^\circ\text{C} \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$, indicating that Pb_3O_4 is stable over a narrow range of only $30^\circ\text{C} \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$ under controlled transformation rate thermal analysis conditions. To elucidate this fourth stage, we turn to the diffraction patterns recorded in the X-ray chamber, where the sample was heated at $\sim 1.5^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$ to reduce the experimental duration. As noted earlier, CRTA requires more than 10 hours—for instance, reaching 300°C takes about 500 minutes, whereas the same temperature is reached in 220 minutes in the X-ray chamber. This compromise inevitably alters the thermodynamic parameters, leading to a shift in the temperature range of the thermal decomposition of Pb_3O_4 into $\alpha\text{-PbO}$. Specifically, the Pb_3O_4 transition temperature is observed at $535^\circ\text{C} \pm 10^\circ\text{C}$ in the X-ray chamber, compared to $410^\circ\text{C} \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$ on the CRTA curve. Nevertheless, the HT-X-ray diffraction study demonstrates that red lead (Pb_3O_4), initially formed from $\alpha\text{-PbO}$, reverts to this phase above $535^\circ\text{C} \pm 10^\circ\text{C}$. We therefore conclude that Pb_3O_4 is metastable in air. Otto noted that the $\text{Pb}_3\text{O}_4\text{-PbO-O}_2$ system is readily reversible under controlled atmospheres, though he provided no experimental evidence¹⁰. In our case, this reversibility is a key factor for both the preparation of red lead and its long-term stability as a pigment. Accordingly, the fourth stage observed on the CRTA curve can be ascribed to the transformation of Pb_3O_4 into $\alpha\text{-PbO}$. In addition, at $560^\circ\text{C} \pm 10^\circ\text{C}$, the X-ray diffraction patterns reveal the transformation of $\alpha\text{-PbO}$ into $\beta\text{-PbO}$. Taken together, these results indicate that the fourth decomposition stage corresponds to the following two transformations.

The first reaction pathway is consistent with the thermal analysis, which shows a clear mass loss between $410^\circ\text{C} \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$ and $460^\circ\text{C} \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$. The second pathway most likely accounts for the plateau observed on the CRTA curve, extending from $460^\circ\text{C} \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$ to $650^\circ\text{C} \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$.

Cultural interpretation

Theophile's 12th-century recipe describes preparing Pb_3O_4 by heating ceruse on hot coals until the powder turns completely red. But what does "red" correspond to in terms of crystalline phases? To address this question, we heated PbCO_3 samples in a furnace at temperatures ranging from 200 to 650°C at a high rate of $10^\circ\text{C}\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$. Each sample was subsequently analysed by photography and X-ray diffraction to characterize its colour and to identify the crystalline phases formed as a function of temperature (Table 1).

Table 1

Colours and crystalline phases of cerussite (PbCO_3) samples as a function of annealing temperature. For each temperature interval, the sample on the left corresponds to the minimum temperature, while the sample on the right corresponds to the maximum temperature.

The sequence of phases observed with increasing temperature is fully consistent with those identified in the HT-X-ray diffraction study. Specifically, we observe the successive formation of $\text{PbCO}_3\cdot 2\text{PbO}$, litharge ($\alpha\text{-PbO}$), minium (Pb_3O_4), its reversion to litharge ($\alpha\text{-PbO}$), and finally massicot ($\beta\text{-PbO}$). The stability ranges of these phases closely match those revealed *in situ*. Table 1 further highlights that the samples display various red to orange hues between 300 and 600°C. These colors may arise not only from Pb_3O_4 , which appears orange, but also from mixtures of phases such as $\text{PbCO}_3\cdot 2\text{PbO}$ and $\alpha\text{-PbO}$. This complexity is critical for interpreting the red tones found in medieval pictorial works. Indeed, our results show that the "red" coloration of lead compounds is not unique: *in situ* analyses of lead-based red pigments must account for both the presence and the absence of Pb_3O_4 .

It should also be recalled that the present study focused on cerussite (PbCO_3). However, the historical term "ceruse" also designates hydrocerussite ($2\text{PbCO}_3\cdot\text{Pb}(\text{OH})_2$), or more commonly, mixtures of cerussite and hydrocerussite. We therefore plan to extend this investigation to the thermal decomposition of $2\text{PbCO}_3\cdot\text{Pb}(\text{OH})_2$ and of $\text{PbCO}_3/2\text{PbCO}_3\cdot\text{Pb}(\text{OH})_2$ mixtures, in order to better understand the phases actually present in medieval lead-based red pigments.

CONCLUSION

We have investigated the chemical mechanisms underlying pigment preparation using advanced thermal and structural characterization techniques. Following a 12th-century recipe, we examined the synthesis of minium by combining Controlled Transformation Rate Thermal Analysis (CRTA) with high-temperature diffraction. Our results demonstrate that “minium,” commonly identified with red lead (Pb_3O_4), can in fact correspond either to pure Pb_3O_4 or to mixtures of PbCO_3 , $\text{PbCO}_3 \cdot 2\text{PbO}$, α - PbO , and β - PbO . In some cases, lead-based red pigments may even be entirely devoid of Pb_3O_4 . This finding is crucial for interpreting *in situ* analyses of medieval red painting materials.

CONFLICTS OF INTEREST

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

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